

Sustainable Development Goals Assessment of Alternative Acetic Acid Synthesis Routes

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ABSTRACT

Acetic acid is an important bulk chemical and one of the major downstream products of methanol. However, it has received less attention from an environmental sustainability perspective. Here, we evaluate the absolute sustainability of several acetic acid synthesis routes, considering both fossil and renewable feedstocks. More specifically, we studied the business-as-usual (BAU) methanol carbonylation and the novel, low technology readiness level (TRL) methane carboxylation and semi-artificial photosynthesis routes. Using process simulation and life cycle assessment (LCA), our results reveal that the alternative routes have the potential to outperform the fossil BAU in at least 14 out of the 16 evaluated impact categories. However, despite the overall improvements, their performance in SDGs 3, 6, 13, 14 and 15 remains poor in any of the studied scenarios, which could potentially be addressed by hybridizing fossil and renewable feedstocks. All in all, our analysis underscores the importance of absolute sustainability to contextualize the environmental footprint of alternative chemical synthesis pathways, going beyond climate change to embrace a broader sense of categories relative to absolute thresholds.

Keywords: green acetic acid, alternative chemical synthesis pathways, semi-artificial photosynthesis (SAP), sustainable development goals (SDGs), absolute environmental sustainability assessment (AESA)

1. INTRODUCTION

Identifying pathways to replace fossil carbon with renewable carbon (i.e., captured CO₂, chemical waste and biomass) in chemical production is one of the most sought-after solutions for mitigating the greenhouse gas emissions associated with the chemical industry [1]. However, while this shift to renewable carbon often reduces CO₂ emissions, it can also lead to burden shifting, where improvements in one environmental category come at the expense of worsening others [2].

Acetic acid is an important chemical with an annual demand of over 17 Mt and serves applications, including the synthesis of plastics, dyes, insecticides and drugs. The standard route to synthesize acetic acid relies on fossil natural gas-based methanol and carbon monoxide in the so-called Cativa process, involving four energy-intensive reaction steps [3]. In the context of sustainable acetic acid synthesis, existing environmental studies are scarce and primarily focus on carbon footprint, rarely ad-

ressing other impact categories [4-7]. Moreover, current studies employ conventional life cycle assessment (LCA), which evaluates the relative differences against a benchmark, often set by the standard fossil-based process. While this methodology is useful for comparing technologies, it fails to capture the true environmental implications of the assessed processes at an Earth-system level. Consequently, absolute environmental sustainability assessment (AESA) methods are gaining popularity [8]. These methods are built on the concept of planetary boundaries (PBs), which define the safe operating space (SOS) for humanity to interact with the planet, enabling direct comparisons with the Earth's carrying capacity [9].

To address this research gap, here we compare the environmental performance of alternative, more efficient, single-step acetic acid synthesis routes with both fossil and green-based conventional processes. Moreover, for the first time, we assess the absolute sustainability level of these synthesis pathways based on the Sustainable

Figure 1: Assessed acetic acid synthesis scenarios.

Development Goals (SDGs), which are computed considering the transgression levels attained relative to the PBs [10].

Our results uncover that despite significantly improving climate change impacts, in addition to other 13 impact categories, none of the studied alternative acetic acid synthesis routes can simultaneously stay within the SOS of the impact categories connected to the SDGs. Moreover, we highlight the potential of hybridizing the feedstocks to enhance their environmental performance.

2. METHODOLOGY

We study five acetic acid synthesis pathways from an absolute sustainability perspective (Figure 1). These scenarios combine three different technologies (business-as-usual, BAU; gas-to-acid, GTA and semi-artificial photosynthesis, SAP), with two different feedstocks: fossil-based (natural gas, coal power plant captured CO₂) and renewable (wind-powered electrolytic green H₂ and direct air captured (DAC) CO₂). We use process simulation (Aspen Plus v12) and literature data to model all proposed scenarios. An overview of the routes is shown in

Figure 1.

For the life cycle assessment (LCA), we follow the guidelines of the ISO 140040/44 framework [11]. We perform a cradle-to-gate assessment with a cut-off attributional approach for acetic acid synthesis, with a functional unit of 1 kg of acetic acid. The foreground system is based on energy and material streams extracted from process simulations developed using Aspen Plus v12, and was retrieved from a previous work [4]. The background system is defined from the Ecoinvent v3.9.1 [12] database and includes all upstream activities related to electricity, energy and raw material production. The life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) is computed with Brightway2 v2.4.6 [13] using the EF v3.1 (15 impact categories) and LANCA v2.5 (land use) methods for the analysis.

The AESA is carried out following the methodology developed by Sala and collaborators [10]. Using Eq.(1), we quantify the transgression level (TL) of category i (TL_i) based on the environmental impact of category i per kg of acetic acid ($impact_i$) and the global demand of acetic acid in 2022 ($market^{acetic}$, 17.48 Mt). This calculation is performed relative to the PB of said category i (PB_i),

Figure 2: Overview of the absolute sustainability results for the studied scenarios. The background colors showcase the level of transgression: SOS, safe operating space (green), UZ, uncertainty zone (yellow); RZ, risk zone (red). Scenarios are defined in Figure 1.

and is multiplied by a downscaling factor (DF). This downscaling factor (Eq.(2)) allocates a fraction of the total PBs to acetic acid production based on some sharing principles [14]. Here, we adopt a utilitarian approach based on the global market value of acetic acid in 2022 (GVA^{acetic} , 14.15 B\$) and the world (GVA^{world} , 88570 B\$) gross value added (GVA) for the same year. Finally, we link the TL of each impact category to the SDGs following the guidelines outlined in Sala et. al [10].

$$TL_i = \frac{impact_i \cdot market^{acetic}}{PB_i \cdot DF} \quad \forall i \in I \quad (1)$$

$$DF = \frac{GVA^{acetic}}{GVA^{world}} \quad (2)$$

We consider that the level of impact on an SDG is within the associated thresholds when the TL of every impact category associated with that SDG is below one, that is, it operates within the allocated fraction of the PB, also referred to as the SOS [15, 16]. Values of the TL between one and two are considered within the so-called uncertainty zone, while values over two belong to the risk zone.

3. RESULTS

As seen in Figure 2, the fossil BAU scenario is outperformed in 14 out of the 16 studied categories by all the proposed alternative synthesis routes, while the fossil GTA and the SAP scenarios perform better in 15 of them. Overall, most of the synthesis pathways are unable to operate within all the thresholds of all the impact categories linked to an SDG, except for the fossil BAU and GTA in SDG 15 (life on land), and SAP attaining SDG 6 (clean water and sanitation). Across scenarios, SDG 3 (good health and well-being) is hindered by high impacts, well into the risk zone, of particulate matter; SDG 6 is affected by high freshwater ecotoxicity levels; SDG 13, (climate action) suffers from high fossil resource use; SDG 14 (life below water) is adversely affected by freshwater eutrophication levels and, finally, the SOS associated with SDG 15 is transgressed from high mineral and metals resource use.

Despite the fossil BAU scenario performing worse in most cases, it already operates within the SOS in 9 out of 16 categories: ionizing radiation, non-cancer human toxicity, cancer human toxicity, marine eutrophication, mineral and metals resource use, acidification, terrestrial eutrophication, land use, water use and ozone depletion. In contrast, it transgresses the SOS (uncertainty zone) for photochemical ozone formation, and it is well into the risk zone in the remaining five categories: particulate matter, freshwater eutrophication, freshwater ecotoxicity, fossil

Figure 3: Transgressed impact categories process contributions.

resource use and climate change.

By switching the feedstock to green methanol and carbon monoxide synthesized from DAC CO₂ and renewable electricity, the green-DAC BAU scenario shows improvements over its fossil analog in all categories except cancer human toxicity and mineral and metals resource use. However, it is worth noting that the absolute sustainability assessment reveals that for cancer human toxicity, this collateral damage occurs within the limits of the SOS. Despite these overall improvements, the green-DAC BAU scenario is still unable to stay within the SOS of

any SDG, as the impacts on particulate matter, freshwater eutrophication, mineral and metals resource use, freshwater ecotoxicity and fossil resource use, associated with SDGs 3, 6, 15, 14 and 13, respectively, transgress the maximum threshold.

The fossil GTA, that is, the direct synthesis of acetic acid from methane (natural gas) and coal power plant-captured CO₂, outperforms the fossil BAU in all categories due to the reduced energy and material requirements of the one-step process compared to the four steps required for the standard synthesis. However, despite this

excellent performance, SDGs 3, 6, 13 and 14 lie still outside the SOS due to high impacts in the categories cited above. On the other hand, SDG 15 is within the SOS due to a particularly low mineral and metals resource use impact compared to the other scenarios. The green variant of the GTA, which uses DAC CO₂ and renewable energy, performs slightly better than the green-DAC BAU scenario but also transgresses the SOS in all categories studied.

Finally, the SAP using DAC CO₂ as a carbon source emerges as one of the best-performing synthesis routes, being the only pathway to operate within the SOS in freshwater ecotoxicity and thus attaining SDG 6. Conversely, this scenario also exhibits the highest impact on mineral and metal resource use due to the utilization of solar power, batteries and specialized infrastructure, as detailed below.

Figure 3 shows the material and energy contributions of the transgressed impact categories for all evaluated scenarios. Overall, the main sources of impact in all categories for the fossil BAU are the raw materials, methanol and carbon monoxide, followed by very small contributions from process heating and electricity. From these results, it is evident that fossil carbon monoxide single-handedly prevents staying within the SOS of SDGs 3, 6, 13 and 14, while the contribution from methanol is much lower. On the contrary, for the green-DAC BAU scenario, green methanol shows overall higher impacts than green carbon monoxide, especially in mineral and metals resource use (SDG 15), particulate matter (SDG 3), freshwater ecotoxicity (SDG 6) and freshwater eutrophication (SDG 14). These results suggest that partially shifting to green carbon monoxide from renewable electricity and captured CO₂ could significantly improve the performance of the BAU. More specifically, this hybrid configuration could help operate within the SOS of SDG 6, particularly for photochemical ozone formation, without causing significant burden-shifting (i.e., the collateral damage remains below the SOS).

The GTA process shows some parallelism with the BAU. The main impact contributions of the fossil variant of the GTA are the raw materials, methane from natural gas and CO₂ captured from a coal power plant, with negligible contributions from energy. However, CO₂ dominates in most of the transgressed categories (particulate matter, photochemical ozone formation, climate change, freshwater ecotoxicity and eutrophication). In contrast, the green-DAC GTA suffers from high impacts from synthetic methane. Hence, shifting to a hybrid natural gas with DAC CO₂ GTA could potentially help the technology operate within the SOS of SDGs 6, 14 and 15 despite still using fossil methane as feedstock.

Finally, the SAP scenario behaves differently depending on the impact category with DAC CO₂ being the

most important contribution in air, water and fossil resource use-related categories. However, renewable solar electricity and the borosilicate/aluminum photochemical reactor account for over 90% of the impacts on mineral and metal resource use.

From these results, we can infer that the hybridization of fossil and renewable feedstocks could potentially help operate within the SOS of a higher number of SDGs, such as SDGs 6, 14 and 15. More specifically, using fossil methanol with green carbon monoxide in the BAU, or fossil methane with DAC CO₂ in the GTA, could minimize the trade-offs derived from using electrolytic hydrogen and renewable electricity of a hypothetical complete shift to renewable energy sources.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we studied the absolute sustainability of alternative acetic acid synthesis routes and compared them to the BAU using fossil methanol and carbon monoxide. Our results show that all evaluated acetic acid synthesis pathways outperform the fossil BAU in terms of climate change impact and 13 other categories. However, burden-shifting still manifests in two categories: human toxicity, and minerals and metals resource use. The AESA reveals that the human toxicity collateral damage occurs within the SOS, rendering it less important. Despite the overall improvements in most impact categories, all the evaluated scenarios transgress at least one of the impact categories associated with the assessed SDGs. However, hybridization of the feedstocks could help in balancing the trade-offs, with a fossil-renewable hybrid GTA scenario potentially operating within the SOS of SDGs 6, 14 and 15. All in all, we show how it is possible to improve the sustainability level of acetic acid synthesis and demonstrate that AESAs provide very valuable insights in the evaluation of alternative synthesis pathways.

ABBREVIATIONS

AESA, absolute environmental sustainability assessment; BAU, business-as-usual; DAC, direct air capture; GTA, gas-to-acid; LCA, life cycle assessment; LCIA, life cycle impact assessment; SAP, semi-artificial photosynthesis; SDGs, sustainable development goals; SOS, safe operating space; TL, transgression level; TRL, technology readiness level

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